

Table S1. Details of localities from where *Leptocoris tagalicus* individuals were collected for this study.

Host plant	Site	State/territory	Lat	Long	Experiment
<i>A. tomentosus</i>	BSR	Queensland	-27.74	153.18	1
<i>A. tomentosus</i>	SA	Queensland	-27.53	152.98	1
<i>C. grandiflorum</i>	DGB	Queensland	-27.71	153.19	1
<i>C. grandiflorum</i>	WR:IR	New South Wales	-28.88	153.30	2
<i>C. grandiflorum</i>	KD:VR	New South Wales	-30.44	153.01	2
<i>C. grandiflorum</i>	LPBR	Queensland	-27.52	153.01	2
<i>C. halicacabum</i>	DLC	Northern Territory	-13.77	130.71	2
<i>C. halicacabum</i>	MWK	Northern Territory	-12.65	132.57	2
<i>C. halicacabum</i>	EAR	Northern Territory	-12.43	132.97	2
<i>C. halicacabum</i>	MFTP	Northern Territory	-13.75	130.70	2
<i>C. grandiflorum</i>	SR	Queensland	-27.55	152.73	2

Table S2. Summary of GLM for *Leptocoris tagalicus* egg production.

	Estimate	SE	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	5.157905	0.094405	54.63612	4.8E-111
crossTypeAG_inter	-0.28552	0.146266	-1.95209	0.05
crossTypeAG_F1	0.334299	0.119284	2.802541	0.005
crossTypeCH_inter	-0.36041	0.133138	-2.70702	0.007
crossTypeCH_F1	0.248305	0.137276	1.808808	0.07
crossTypegrandiflorum_control	-0.06285	0.113801	-0.55228	0.58
crossTypehalicacabum_control	-0.1071	0.127515	-0.8399	0.4

Table S3. Summary of GLM for *Leptocoris tagalicus* relative fecundity.

	Estimate	SE	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	-0.88083	0.131564	-6.69506	2.89E-10
crossTypeAG_inter	-0.3691	0.208957	-1.76641	0.08
crossTypeAG_F1	0.326005	0.166495	1.958051	0.05
crossTypeCH_inter	-0.2572	0.180963	-1.42126	0.15
crossTypeCH_F1	0.477055	0.180707	2.639938	0.009
crossTypegrandiflorum_control	0.004625	0.156973	0.029465	0.98
crossTypehalicacabum_control	0.141282	0.168645	0.837748	0.4

Table S4. Summary of GLM for *Leptocoris tagalicus* development time.

	Estimate	SE	t value	PR(> t)
Intercept	3.317389	0.016937	195.87	2E-16
crossTypeAG_F1	-0.00547	0.024358	-0.22	0.8
crossTypealectryon_control	0.005846	0.02211	0.26	0.7
crossTypeCH_inter	0.086702	0.021932	3.95	7.71E-05
crossTypeCH_F1	0.052555	0.025347	2.07	0.03
crossTypegrandiflorum_control	0.05172	0.020214	2.56	0.01
crossTypehalicacabum_control	0.115307	0.021456	5.37	7.70E-08